

RATE AND TEMPERATURE EFFECTS ON MODE II INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS

T.J. Chapman, A.J. Smiley, and R. B. Pipes
Center for Composite Materials
University of Delaware
Newark, DE 19716, U.S.A.

ABSTRACT

Presented in this paper is an experimental investigation of the effects of loading rate and temperature on Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness of graphite/PEEK (APC-2) and graphite/epoxy (AS4/3501-6) composite materials. The experimental work was performed using the End Notched Flexure (ENF) test for a shear displacement rate range of 4.2×10^{-6} to 9.2×10^{-2} m/s at room temperature and 4.2×10^{-6} to 4.2×10^{-3} m/s at elevated and reduced temperatures (-50°C and 100°C for both materials and 150°C for APC-2 only).

For APC-2, both ductile and brittle crack growth was observed with the type of growth present dependent upon both rate and temperature. High rates at room temperature caused a fracture toughness decline while a less significant drop at 150°C is attributable to surpassing the glass transition temperature. A possible combined effect as rate increases and temperature decreases was indicated by a decline in G_{IIc} . The AS4/3501-6 material displayed brittle crack growth at all loading rates and temperatures. At room temperature, G_{IIc} remained nearly constant for lower rates and dropped to a plateau at the highest rates. Fracture toughness increased with temperature at lower rates.

INTRODUCTION

In the past, continuous fiber composites have been utilized for weight savings in secondary structures. Recent research developments in composites have led to strength and stiffness properties comparable to metals. Thus, major applications of composite materials today are primary load-bearing structures. One limitation of these materials is relatively low resistance to interlaminar flaw initiation and propagation. Fracture toughness, a measure of resistance to defect propagation, is dependent upon various material and external factors. For composites with polymer matrices, these factors include: constituent properties, fiber/matrix interface properties, rate of loading, environmental conditions (i.e. temperature, moisture) and loading mode (i.e. tensile, shear, tearing). The effects of these factors must be measured and characterized before the fracture behavior of composite materials can be fully understood.

The Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) test for studying Mode I (opening mode) interlaminar fracture toughness and crack growth in composite materials has been studied extensively [1-3]. The effects of loading rate on Mode I fracture toughness have been researched by Daniel et. al. [4], Smiley et. al. [5], and Berglund [6]. Temperature effects on

this property are discussed by Bitner et. al. [7]. The End Notched Flexure (ENF) test, used to measure Mode II (shear mode) interlaminar fracture toughness in composites, was introduced by Russell [8]. The ENF test geometry has been utilized by Murri et. al. [9] and Carlsson et. al. [10] to investigate the effects of specimen preparation and data reduction methods on G_{IIc} . The same test geometry was employed by Russell and Street [11,12] to study the combined influence of moisture and temperature on G_{IIc} .

The deformation behavior of the matrix is the primary factor governing the interlaminar fracture toughness of a polymer-based composite material. A relation between the Mode I fracture toughness of neat polymers and the Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of composites with corresponding polymer matrices was investigated by Hunston [13]. Loading rate and temperature effects on the fracture behavior of epoxy and PEEK polymeric resins have been shown to be quite significant [14,15].

The purpose of this research was to investigate combined temperature and rate sensitivity of Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness in continuous fiber composites. The ENF test geometry was employed to conduct Mode II fracture tests on graphite/epoxy and graphite/PEEK composite specimens. The temperature and rate effects were examined through visual observation of crack growth behavior, calculation of critical strain energy release rate, and microscopic examination of the ENF fracture surfaces.

EXPERIMENTAL

The ENF geometry, as proposed by Russell [8], is shown in Figure 1. The composite beam is unidirectional and contains a mid-plane crack at one end. With a half span length, L , of 50 mm, and initial crack length, a , of 25 mm, the crack length to half span ratio is 0.5. Testing consists of the application of a load, P , at the span midpoint, introducing a deflection, δ . The Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness can be calculated based upon the recorded load-displacement response of the beam through the onset of fracture.

Figure 1. End Notched Flexure (ENF) test configuration.

Specimen dimensions were 25 mm by 100 mm with 26 ply thicknesses. A double layer of 0.025 mm Kapton film was inserted at the mid-plane of each panel prior to processing to produce a starter crack from which propagation would occur. Since the presence of the Kapton film causes a resin-rich region which blunts the crack tip and induces unreasonably high G_{IIc} results [10], a precracking procedure, accomplished by wedging a razor blade between the double layer of film of a clamped ENF specimen, was employed.

APC-2, a thermoplastic composite material produced by Imperial Chemical Industries, was the fiber-reinforced PEEK system tested. This reinforced polymer requires a high processing temperature (380°C) and rapid cooling rate (greater than 10°C/min) to attain sufficient crystallinity and material properties. Internally-cooled platens and a compression press were used to produce a cooling rate of approximately 40°C/min during processing of the APC-2 panels. AS4/3501-6,a Hercules Co. thermoset, was the graphite fiber-reinforced epoxy

composite tested. The cure cycle recommended by the supplier was utilized to process the prepreg material in an autoclave. All processing was completed at the Center for Composite Materials.

The room temperature ENF tests were performed at shear displacement rates ranging from 4.2×10^{-6} to 9.2×10^{-2} m/s. Temperature testing at 100°C , 150°C (APC-2 only), and -50°C was completed for speeds of 4.2×10^{-6} to 4.2×10^{-3} m/s. Each sample, tested at a constant crosshead speed, yielded one data point. Rates ranging from 4.2×10^{-6} to 4.2×10^{-3} m/s were attained using an Instron 1125 static test frame. A hydraulic Instron 1322 dynamic test system and a high rate data acquisition system were employed for the tests at rates from 3.2×10^{-3} to 9.2×10^{-2} m/s. Elevated temperatures were attained with a Thermotron F4-CH-LN₂-S oven while the reduced temperature was reached by introducing liquid nitrogen into the oven.

DATA REDUCTION

Strain energy release rate, G [16], is a quantitative measure of the interlaminar fracture toughness of a material.

$$G = \frac{1}{w} \frac{d}{da} (F-U) \quad (1)$$

where F = work done by an external force, U = stored elastic strain energy, a = crack length, and w = specimen width. The strain energy release rate is also related to the change in compliance with extension of a crack [16],

$$G_C = \frac{P^2}{2w} \frac{dC}{da} \quad (2)$$

where P = magnitude of external force and C = beam compliance.

A beam theory formulation for G_{IIC} was derived by Russell [8] and was extended to include shear deformation in a paper by Carlsson et. al. [17]. Thus, the ENF beam compliance can be expressed as

$$C = \frac{\delta}{P} = \frac{(2L^3 + 3a^3)}{8E_1 wh^3} \left(1 + \frac{2(1.2L + 0.9a)h^2 E_1}{(2L^3 + 3a^3)G_{13}} \right) \quad (3)$$

where E_1 = material flexural modulus, G_{13} = interlaminar shear modulus, and h = beam half thickness. Differentiating compliance with respect to crack length and combining with equation (2) yields

$$G_{IIC} = \frac{9a^2 P_C^2}{16E_1 w^2 h^3} \left(1 + 0.2 \left(\frac{E_1}{G_{13}} \right) \left(\frac{h}{a} \right)^2 \right) \quad (4)$$

where P_C = critical load necessary for crack growth.

Thus, the Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness can be computed from the geometric and material properties of each specimen and the critical applied load.

Based upon a finite element analysis of the ENF specimen, Gillespie et. al. [18] proposed that beam theory data reduction schemes, depending upon specimen geometry and type of material, may produce a fracture toughness as much as 20 to 40 percent below the actual value. A finite element correction for the beam theory formula was developed [18] to improve the data reduction process.

$$G_{IIC}^{FE} = \frac{9a^2 P_C^2}{16E_1 w^2 h^3} \left(\alpha + \beta \left(\frac{E_1}{G_{13}} \right) \left(\frac{h}{a} \right)^2 \right) \quad (5)$$

Numerical results are used to find the constant parameters α and β based upon the specimen half span, L , and the specimen thickness, $2h$. The material properties and parameter values used for this investigation may be found in Table 1. All geometric variables and critical applied loads are measured for each sample.

TABLE 1

Parameters and material properties utilized in data reduction for G_{IIC} .

Material	α	β	E_1 (GPa)	G_{13} (GPa)
APC-2	0.969	2.615	115	4.48
AS4/3501-6	0.969	2.615	128	6.41

In the case of high rate ENF testing, kinetic energy may be a significant energy-absorbing mechanism and, therefore, must be included in the energy balance. Consideration of kinetic energy produces a revised definition of G_{IIC} [16].

$$G_{IIC} = \frac{1}{w} \frac{d}{da} (F-U-T) \quad (6)$$

where T = total kinetic energy of the ENF sample.

The kinetic energy contribution for an ENF geometry of $a/L = 0.5$ was determined by Smiley [19]. Thus, accounting for this additional energy, fracture toughness may be expressed as

$$G_{IIC} = \frac{9a^2 P_C^2}{16E_1 w^2 h^3} \left(\alpha + \beta \left(\frac{E_1}{G_{13}} \right) \left(\frac{h}{a} \right)^2 \right) + 0.078 \rho h \dot{\delta}^2 \quad (7)$$

where ρ = material density and $\dot{\delta}$ = displacement rate.

G_{IIC} must be measured as a function of shear displacement rate in order to study the effect of loading rate on Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness. In the region near the crack tip, the shear displacement rate, \dot{u}_{CT} , represents the relative sliding velocity of the surfaces at an arbitrarily small distance, ϵ (chosen as 2 ply thicknesses or 0.25 mm), from the crack tip. Using Timoshenko beam theory [20], the rate of relative sliding or shear displacement rate near the crack tip is derived.

$$\dot{u}_{CT} = \frac{24 \dot{\delta} h a \epsilon}{(2L^3 + 3a^3)} \quad (8)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characterization of the Mode II fracture behavior was performed for a large range of crosshead speeds at elevated, reduced, and room temperatures. For an ENF geometry of $a/L = 0.5$ as studied in this paper, it has been shown [17] that the crack driving force increases with

crack length ($dG/da > 0$). Therefore, unstable crack growth is expected for all testing. Figure 2 includes typical load-displacement responses obtained from testing.

The carbon fiber-reinforced PEEK composite, APC-2, unstable critical crack growth for all loading rates tested at -50°C , primarily all rates at room temperature (a couple of specimens at the lowest rate were exceptions), and the two highest rates at 100°C and 150°C . However, the material displayed various degrees of subcritical crack growth which resulted in nonlinear load-displacement responses during testing (Figure 2a). The degree of nonlinearity in the response appears to decrease as loading rate increases and temperature decreases (Figure 2b). At displacement rates above 3.2×10^{-3} m/s, virtually no nonlinearity was observed and the response is linear elastic (Figure 2c). Subcritical crack growth in Mode II interlaminar fracture was observed by Carlsson et. al. [10] who proposed that the nonlinear behavior could be attributed to both inelastic material response (viscoelastic effects and material yielding) and stable crack extension. For all rates and temperatures, the applied load at the onset of rapid fracture was employed as the critical load, P_c , in the data reduction.

Figure 2. Typical Mode II load-displacement responses.

APC-2 exhibited stable crack growth at the two lowest rates at elevated temperatures as indicated by the load-displacement response shown in Figure 2d. Nonlinearity prior to fracture was also observed for these samples.

The carbon fiber-reinforced epoxy, AS4/3501-6, showed virtually no subcritical crack growth or nonlinear behavior at any rate or temperature. Unstable crack extension similar to that observed for APC-2 at high rates was typical for all AS4/3501-6 samples (Figure 2c). As before, critical loads were measured at the onset of crack growth.

The data reduction method previously presented (equation (7)) was used to calculate experimental values of G_{IIc} . For the range of rates tested, the kinetic energy contribution was insignificant ($< 0.01\%$) in comparison to other energy terms. Known material properties, measured specimen geometric dimensions, and experimental critical load, P_c , were the required variables. The latter value was read directly from the load-displacement curve for the low loading rates (less than 4.2×10^{-3} m/s). At higher rates, the very small time span of the test caused inaccurate critical load measurements since the load instrumentation could not respond quickly enough. Therefore, by assuming linear elastic response, P_c is computed from the specimen compliance, C , determined from equation (3), and critical displacement, δ_c , taken from the load-displacement curve.

$$P_c = \delta_c / C \quad (9)$$

Since experimental variables were measured at the point of initial crack growth, the fracture toughness calculated is the initiation fracture energy. As seen in Figures 3 through 6, APC-2 has a higher toughness than AS4/3501-6 for all temperatures and loading rates considered. This is due to the tougher PEEK matrix employed in APC-2.

The data illustrated in Figure 3 shows that loading rate is an important factor in Mode II fracture of both composite systems. For the lowest four or five decades of loading rate, G_{IIc} is nearly constant (1.9 kJ/m² for APC-2 and 0.46 kJ/m² for AS4/3501-6).

Figure 3. Rate sensitivity of G_{IIc} at room temperature (log-log).

Figure 4. Rate sensitivity of G_{IIc} at room temperature (linear-log).

At higher rates, G_{IIc} decreases with rate as illustrated along the linear abscissa employed in Figure 4. The fracture toughness of APC-2 drops monotonically to 0.40 kJ/m² while G_{IIc} of AS4/3501-6 decreases to 0.06 kJ/m². This leveling supports a conclusion of a minimum toughness at this value. The AS4/3501-6 appears to have reached a minimum toughness. However, further experiments at higher rates would be required for verification.

Figure 5. Temperature sensitivity of G_{IIc} for APC-2.

Figure 6. Temperature sensitivity of G_{IIc} for AS4/3501-6.

Figure 5 shows the results for the G_{IIc} of APC-2 as a function of loading rate at the four temperatures tested. For the three lowest rates and three lower temperatures, no rate and temperature effects are apparent. However, at the highest rate and reduced temperature, a decrease in fracture toughness was observed as a result of the brittle nature of the material at these test conditions. Because the glass transition temperature had been exceeded, the fracture toughness at 150°C was below that measured at lower temperatures. Further testing at lower temperatures and higher rates is necessary to confirm the rate and temperature effects present at high rates at -50°C.

The data recorded for AS4/3501-6 is presented in Figure 6 for the four loading rates and three temperatures tested. The results indicate that a decrease in temperature causes a decrease in G_{IIc} . This can be attributed to the fact that the epoxy matrix embrittles at decreased temperatures. The numerical values obtained were approximately 0.5 kJ/m^2 at -50°C with an increase to 0.7 kJ/m^2 at 100°C .

A scanning electron microscope (SEM) was used to examine the fracture surfaces of the ENF specimens and characterize the fracture mechanisms and deformations produced at the onset of Mode II crack growth. Two types of deformation were observed in APC-2 for the range of rates and temperatures tested. Slow ductile tearing shown in Figure 7a was observed for samples tested at elevated temperatures and at low rates. This matrix deformation could be the cause of the nonlinearity present in the load-displacement curves shown previously. Brittle crack growth which produces little plastic deformation was exhibited by APC-2 at reduced temperature and at the high rates for which cracks grew quickly and unstably. Figure 7b is a typical example of this fracture behavior. The thermoset composite, AS4/3501-6, displayed virtually no change in fracture mechanism from one set of test conditions to another. As evident in Figure 7c, the plastic deformation which takes place in the highly crosslinked epoxy matrix is much less significant than that in the thermoplastic PEEK polymer. Hackles of resin material on the fracture surface are a primary feature of the brittle Mode II deformation of AS4/3501-6.

Figure 7. Mode II fracture behavior of APC-2 and AS4/3501-6.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

APC-2, a graphite/PEEK composite material, and AS4/3501-6, a graphite/epoxy material, were tested to study Mode II interlaminar fracture over a wide range of loading rates at elevated, reduced, and room temperatures. The influences of rate and temperature were characterized by examining load-displacement response, fracture toughness values, and microscopic deformation behavior of the fractured test specimens.

The thermoplastic material, APC-2, displayed rate and temperature dependent nonlinear load-displacement response caused by the presence of subcritical crack growth prior to fracture. The degree of nonlinearity decreased as temperature decreased and loading rate increased. At displacement rates beyond $3.2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m/s}$, the response was nearly linear elastic. Stable crack growth was present for all other conditions. Microscopic study of fracture surfaces displayed ductile deformation behavior of the polymer with extensive plastic deformation at low rates and room and elevated temperatures. At other conditions for which no subcritical crack growth was observed, brittle deformation of the polymer was present. At room temperature, the fracture toughness of APC-2 was approximately 1.9 kJ/m^2 for low to intermediate shear displacement rates after which a monotonic decrease to 0.40 kJ/m^2 at $7.8 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m/s}$ was measured. This drop

in toughness can be attributed to the decrease in plastic deformation as rate increases. Temperature effects were observed at 150°C for which a toughness decrease occurred due to heating beyond the glass transition temperature. At the highest rate tested at -50°C, a drop in G_{IIc} was recorded, indicating a possible combined effect of high rate and low temperature.

AS4/3501-6, a thermoset composite, displayed virtually no nonlinear behavior over the range of rates and temperatures tested. The fracture toughness at room temperature showed rate dependence with a relatively constant value of 0.46 kJ/m² for shear displacement rates below 2.7×10^{-6} m/s. Further increase in rate produced a decrease in G_{IIc} to a plateau of 0.06 kJ/m² at the highest test rates. This plateau may imply the existence of a minimum toughness for AS4/3501-6. Temperature appears to be an important variable since the fracture toughness increases from approximately 0.5 kJ/m² at -50°C to 0.7 kJ/m² at 100°C. Microscopic examination of fracture surfaces revealed brittle deformation of the polymer for all loading rates tested.

By characterizing the Mode II interlaminar fracture behavior of composite materials, the effect of impact loading, a common problem in structural applications, can be better understood. Further Mode II testing at higher rates and lower temperatures as well as a study of rate and temperature effects in Mode III fracture would add to the present knowledge. Additionally, the effect of processing conditions (e.g. degree of crystallinity of a thermoplastic matrix) on interlaminar fracture behavior should be investigated.

REFERENCES

1. Whitney, J.M., Browning, C.E., and Hoogsteden, W., A double cantilever beam test for characterizing Mode I delamination of composite materials. Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites, Vol.1, No.4, October 1982, pp.297-330.
2. Wilkins, D.J., Eisenmann, J.R., Camin, R.A., Margoli, W.S., and Benson, R.A., Characterizing delamination growth in graphite/epoxy, Damage in Composite Materials, ASTM STP 775, 1982, p.168.
3. Bascom, W.D., Bullman, G.W., Hunston, D.C. and Jensen, R.M., The width tapered DCB for interlaminar fracture testing. Proc. 29th National SAMPE Symposium, 1982.
4. Daniel, I.M. and Aliyu, A.A., Effects of strain rate on delamination fracture toughness of graphite/epoxy. Delamination and Debonding of Materials, ASTM STP 876, 1982, p.336.
5. Smiley, A.J. and Pipes, R.B., Rate effects on Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness in composite materials. Accepted for publication in Journal of Composite Materials.
6. Berglund, L., Rate effects on the interlaminar toughness of PEEK/carbon fiber composites. Licentiate Thesis No.54, Linköping University, Sweden, 1985.
7. Bitner, J.L., Rushford, J.L., Rose, W.S., Hunston, D.L., and Riew, C.K., Journal of Adhesion, Vol.13, 1981, pp.3-28.
8. Russell, A.J., On the measurement of Mode II interlaminar fracture energies. Defence Research Establishment Pacific, Victoria, B.C., Materials Report 82-0, December 1982.
9. Murri, G.B. and O'Brien, T.K., Interlaminar G_{IIc} evaluation of toughened-resin matrix composites using the end-notched flexure test. Presented at the 26th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Materials Conference, Orlando, Florida, April 15-17, 1985.

10. Carlsson, L.A., Gillespie, J.W., and Trethewey, B., Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness in graphite/epoxy and graphite/PEEK composites. Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites, Vol.5, p.170.
11. Russell, A.J. and Street, K.N., Moisture and temperature effects on the mixed-mode delamination fracture of unidirectional graphite/epoxy. Delamination and Debonding of Materials, ASTM STP 876, 1985, p.349.
12. Russell, A.J. and Street, K.N., Factors affecting the interlaminar fracture energy of graphite/epoxy laminates. Progress in Science and Engineering of Composites, T. Hayashi, K. Kawata and S. Umekawa ed., ICCM-IV, Tokyo, 1982, p.279.
13. Hunston, D.L., Bascom, W.D., Moulton, R.J., Johnston, N.J., Matrix resin effects in composite delamination: Mode I fracture aspects. Presented at the ASTM Conference Toughened Composites, Houston, TX, 13-15 March, 1985.
14. Kinloch, A.J., Shaw, S.J., Tod, D.A., Hunston, D.L., Deformation and fracture behavior of a rubbered-toughened epoxy: 1. microstructure and fracture studies. Polymer, Vol.24, October, 1983.
15. Friedrich, K., Fracture of neat and short fiber reinforced PEEK. To be published.
16. Broek, D., Elementary Engineering Fracture Mechanics, Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, 1982.
17. Carlsson, L.A., Gillespie, J.W., and Pipes, R.B., On the analysis and design of the end notched flexure (ENF) specimen for Mode II testing. Accepted for publication in J. Composite Materials.
18. Gillespie, J.W., Carlsson, L.A. and Pipes, R.B., Finite element analysis of the end notched flexure specimen for measuring Mode II fracture toughness. Accepted for publication in Composite Science and Technology.
19. Smiley, A.J., Rate sensitivity of interlaminar fracture toughness in composite materials. MMAE Thesis, University of Delaware, Newark, DE, 1986.
20. Timoshenko, S.P. and Goodier, J.N., Theory of Elasticity, McGraw-Hill Inc., 1970.